

Table 2. Yield of 23 promising rice cultures at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia, 1988.

Culture	Plant ht (cm)	Days to maturity	Panicles /m ²	Grain yield ^d (t/ha)
IR19661-13-3-2	104.7	130	214	5.1 b
BW267-3	118.2	120	232	6.7 a
IR6023-10-1-1	118.8	125	216	6.3a
CR261-7039-236	96.7	125	239	6.4 a
ROHYB15-WAr-3-3	125.8	145	201	2.9e
BW100	119.3	140	155	2.8 e
BR51-120-2	115.1	140	200	2.7 efg
CR1009	104.2	150	190	2.7 efg
IR9217-58-2-2	98.4	135	228	3.6 d
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	108.5	135	205	3.6 d
Pankaj	106.9	145	196	4.4 c
IR13146-45-2	108.0	135	212	3.8 d
IR8192-31-2-1-2	101.1	140	147	2.4 fg
IR21586-R-31-1	110.4	145	198	2.4 fg
ITA230	102.7	140	217	4.4 c
IR14753-120-3	102.3	125	212	2.3 g
IR29723-88-2-3-3	100.4	140	179	2.3 g
IR33353-64-1-2-1	100.8	125	255	2.2 gh
IR19657-87-3-3	104.7	135	190	2.1 gh
IR4422-480-2-3-3	101.1	135	166	1.8 h
IR31917-31-3-2	95.6	140	171	2.4 fg
IR52	95.2	115	247	1.3 i
IR21836-90-3	107.7	140	208	1.1 i

^aValues followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

CR261-7039-236 are medium. Amylose content is 26-28%.

These four lines are resistant to leaf blast and stem borer. □

Mean cumulative N loss by ammonia volatilization in saturated soil, as influenced by soil amendment, source of N, and application method.

Soil amendment	Cumulative N loss (%)				
	N source			Application method	
	Urea	NCBU	NOCU	Surface applied	Surface mixed
Gypsum	11	11	4	11	6
Pyrite	10	7	4	8	6
Rice straw	12	12	5	13	6
Rice husk	13	13	5	13	7
Control	32	34	10	32	18
LSD (0.05)	Amendment x Source of N 2			Application method 3	

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management

Influence of organic and inorganic amendments, modified urea, and application methods on ammonia volatilization in saturated calcareous soil

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Ammonia volatilization from urea depends on such factors as rate of hydrolysis of urea, concentration of NH₄-N in the soil, and pH. Coating urea with some material can reduce NH₃ volatilization.

We measured NH₃-N volatilization from urea, neem cake-blended urea (NCBU), and neem oil-coated urea (NOCU) from a saturated calcareous soil (pH 8.25, 1.25% organic C, 23.7% CaCO₃, and CEC 19 meq/100 g soil) amended with gypsum, pyrite, rice straw, and rice husks. A forced draft chamber technique was used to trap ammonia.

Three-kg air-dried soil, equilibrated with soil amendments (20 t/ha) for 4 wk under saturated conditions, was placed in 5-liter wide-mouth glass bottles. N was applied at 150 kg/ha on the surface of the soil or mixed in the soil surface (see table for treatments).

The bottles were connected with an air compressor to flush out evolved NH₃ from the soil (4-5 liter/h). The NH₃ was trapped in 2% boric acid mixed with an indicator. Boric acid was titrated against 0.05 NH₂SO₄ at regular intervals for 30 d.

Application of soil amendments significantly reduced cumulative NH₃ volatilization. The reduction in NH₃ loss appears to be due to a lowering of soil pH on equilibration with soil amendments (see figure).

The formation of stable ammonium sulfate in soils amended with gypsum and pyrite may have contributed to reduction of NH₃ loss. Reduction of NH₃ volatilization from soil amended with rice husks and straw may be due to sorption of NH₄⁺ by organic matter.

NH₃ volatilization loss from soils amended with NOCU was lower because a thin layer of neem oil around the prilled urea acted as a physical barrier, reducing the rate of N release and thus the concen-

Soil pH on equilibration with amendments under saturated conditions.

tration of NH_4^+ in the soil. NH_3 volatilization from NCBU and with uncoated urea was the same.

Irrespective of soil amendment and N source, NH_3 volatilization was less when

N was surface mixed rather than surface applied. This may be because more of the surface area of soil organic matter and clay was available for sorption of NH_4^+ -N ions. □

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Effect of gypsum-enriched biogas sludge and farmyard manure (FYM) on rice yield

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We evaluated the effect of biogas sludge and FYM on rice yields in two successive field trials, Jul-Oct 1989 and Nov-Feb 1990. Rice cultivars were IR20 and ADT37.

Soil of the experimental field the first season was clay loam with pH 7.4; EC 0.6 dS/m; 0.44% organic C; and available N, P_2O_5 , K_2O were 225, 14, 312 kg/ha, respectively. Soil of the experimental field the second season was clay loam with pH 7.2; EC 0.5 dS/m; 0.43% organic C; and 238, 23, 314 kg available N, P_2O_5 , K_2O /ha, respectively.

The biogas sludge contained 1.5% N, 0.82% P_2O_5 , and 0.75% K_2O . FYM

contained 0.85% N, 0.35% P_2O_5 , 0.688 K_2O , and 58% water in season 1, and 0.75% N, 0.61% P_2O_5 , 0.63% K_2O , and 57% water in season 2. In both seasons, N, P_2O_5 , and K_2O at 100, 50, and 50 kg/ha were applied as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. The experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications (see table for treatments).

Growth and yield attributes and grain and straw yields were favorably influenced by biogas sludge and FYM both seasons. Added gypsum acted as an absorbent, reducing the moisture content of biogas wet sludge and FYM by 30 and 10%, respectively.

Grain yields were highest with enriched biogas sludge both seasons. The next best was enriched FYM. Enrichment of wet biogas sludge with gypsum increased yields 0.95 and 0.71 t/ha in the first and second seasons, respectively. Enriched FYM increased yields 0.67 and 0.56 t/ha. □

Effect of gypsum-enriched biogas sludge and farmyard manure on rice yield.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²		Filled grains/panicle		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2
Biogas wet sludge (10t/ha)	384	354	98	71	7.5	3.7	13.0	4.9
Biogas dried sludge (10t/ha)	385	365	99	71	7.8	3.8	13.7	5.1
Biogas wet sludge (10t/ha) enriched with 250 kg gypsum/ha	413	412	109	74	8.4	4.4	15.3	6.2
FYM (10t/ha)	341	343	99	72	7.3	3.7	12.6	4.8
FYM (10t/ha) enriched with 250 kg gypsum/ha	385	407	107	74	8.0	4.3	14.7	5.8
Gypsum (250 kg/ha)	330	324	107	70	6.8	3.5	11.5	4.7
Control	324	313	97	70	6.6	3.2	11.0	4.6
LSD(0.05)	1	11	2	2	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.2

Fertilizer management— inorganic sources

Effect of irrigation and nitrogen on transplanted summer rice yield and water use efficiency

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We studied the effect of three irrigation schedules and four N levels on grain yield and water use efficiency of transplanted summer rice (Apr-Jul) 1987-89.

The soil was acidic sandy loam (pH 5.4), low in total N (0.065%), medium in available P_2O_5 (18 kg/ha; Bray and Kurtz No.1), and low in available K_2O (86 kg/ha; neutral ammonium acetate method). The rice variety used was IR50. Phosphate and potash were applied at 20 kg each/ha. Average rainfall during the 3 yr was 688 mm.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Treatments are given in Table 1.

Irrigation schedule had no effect on grain yield. During the summer season, rainfall increased from the early vegeta-

Table 1. Effect of irrigation schedule and N level on grain yield of summer rice in Assam, India.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1987	1988	1989	Pooled
Irrigation				
Continuous submergence	2.2	1.4	2.7	2.1
7 cm water 1DADPW	2.0	1.6	2.7	2.1
7 cm water 3DADPW	2.1	1.6	2.8	2.2
LSD(0.05)	ns	0.05	ns	ns
N level (kg/ha)				
0	2.0	1.7	2.2	1.9
40	2.2	1.4	2.7	2.1
80	2.0	1.5	3.0	2.2
120	2.2	1.5	3.1	2.3
LSD(0.05)	ns	ns	0.12	0.14

^a DADPW = days after disappearance of ponded water.